

Spectrophotometric Determination of Thorium after Solvent Extraction with 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-benzoyl-5-pyrazolone

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Solvent extraction of metals with 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-benzoyl-5-pyrazolone (PMBP) has been reviewed¹. The present author² studied the solvent extraction behaviour of thorium with this reagent. Mirza and Nwabue³ also⁴ used PMBP for the extraction of thorium. The present work aims at estimating thorium present in natural samples (rock and soil) after separation with this reagent.

Results and Discussion

It is observed that thorium(IV) gets extracted with 0.2 M PMBP solution in xylene or toluene in 1–1.5 M HCl medium in single extraction beyond which the extraction decreases. To prevent the extraction of iron(III) which not only consumes most of the reagent but also hinders complete extraction of thorium, it is reduced to iron(II) by adding ascorbic acid to the experimental solution. Zirconium also hinders extraction of thorium. This is obviated, if present, by adding 1 ml of 1 mM ammonium oxalate solution and carrying two extractions with PMBP. U^{VI}, Y^{III}, La^{III}, Ce^{IV}, Eu^{III}, Tb^{III}, and Ti^{IV} do not get extracted and do not interfere under the experimental parameters.

Thorium is completely stripped from the organic phase if shaken with 5–6 M HCl (2 × 10 ml) and can be estimated spectrophotometrically using thoron⁴ or arsenazo(III)⁵ reagents. The method can estimate thorium down to 20 ppm. Quite a few rock samples were analysed by this method. The agreement of ThO₂ values obtained by the present method and radiometric assay values⁶ and also with the recommended values of internationally analysed samples proves the accuracy of the method. It is expected that the method may also prove useful for estimating thorium present in fission products. The method is rapid and more sensitive compared to the conventional classical techniques of separation. Moreover, macroquantities of thorium can be extracted with this reagent.

Experimental

The reagent PMBP was synthesised by the reported methods⁷. Solutions of required concentration were prepared in toluene or xylene. Thorium stock solution (10 mg ml⁻¹ Th) was prepared from pure hydrated thorium nitrate and standardised by titration with standard EDTA Na₂ solution. Experi-

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mental solutions were prepared by diluting this solution. Standard solutions of other metals were prepared by dissolving their suitable salts in water or dilute HCl or were brought into solution by standard methods.

A Varian 634 spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements.

Procedure for solvent extraction: To standard thorium solution (25–500 μg ; 20–30 ml) having an acidity of 1–1.5 M (HCl), were added ascorbic acid (0.5 g) and 10^{-3} M ammonium oxalate (1 ml). Thorium was extracted for 2 min each with 10 ml of 0.2 M PMBP solution. The organic extract was separated and stripped with 5–6 M HCl. In order to test the interference of associated elements, Fe^{III} (100 mg), Y, Eu, La, Ce, Tb, Ti, Zr and U (1 mg each), thorium was extracted in presence of these elements and estimated spectrophotometrically.

Procedure for rock/soil samples: The sample (1 g) was brought into solution by treatment with HF and HNO₃ to dryness and the residue leached with dilute HNO₃. Any residue still left after

leaching was fused with sodium peroxide and mixed with the previous filterate. Th^{IV} was precipitated with ammonium hydroxide, boiled and filtered. The precipitate was dissolved in 1–1.5 M HCl and ascorbic acid (0.5 g) was added to reduce Fe^{III}. When zirconium was suspected to be present, 1 ml of 1 mM ammonium oxalate solution was also added. Thorium was then extracted with PMBP solution, stripped with 5–6 M HCl and estimated spectrophotometrically as above.

References

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